

Stepwise Stability Constants of Cadmium Complexes of Pyridine, β -Picoline, and γ -Picoline

A. G. Desai and M. B. Kabadi

The stepwise stability constants for the cadmium complexes of pyridine, β -picoline, and γ -picoline have been evaluated from the E. M. F. data, utilising the graphical method of Leden. The values for individual complexes with Cd: ligand ratio from 1:1 to 1:3 are as follows:

Cd—pyridine	:	$\beta_1=18$,	$\beta_2=90$,	$\beta_3=195$;
Cd— β -picoline	:	$\beta_1=25.5$,	$\beta_2=146$,	$\beta_3=345$;
Cd— γ -picoline	:	$\beta_1=31.5$,	$\beta_2=147$,	$\beta_3=941$.

The constants have been calculated for aqueous solutions of ionic strength 0.1 at 30°. Similar studies with α -picoline show that if any complexes are formed, they are very weak, probably due to steric hindrance of the $-\text{CH}_3$ group.

Sufficient data are available on the formation constants of metal complexes of aliphatic amines. It is noteworthy, however, that the aromatic amines do not seem to have received much attention from this point of view. Bjerrum, Schwarzenbach, and Sillén ("Stability Constants. Part I. Organic Ligands", the Chemical Society, London, 1957) have recorded a few data on the metal complexes of pyridine and only Ag^+ -complexes of its derivatives. Euler (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2768), Bailar *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 2484), Morinaga (*Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1956, 77, 865), and Liu and Fu (*K'o Hsieh T'ung Pao*, 1957, 23, 718) have determined solution stability constants of Cd^{2+} -pyridine complexes. These results, however, are found to be controversial. The present communication deals with studies in the stepwise stability constants of cadmium complexes of pyridine, β -picoline, and γ -picoline in aqueous medium, utilising a method suggested by Leden (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1941, A188, 160).

EXPERIMENTAL

0.1M- $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ solution was prepared by dissolving CdCO_3 (E. Merck, extra pure) in 0.2M- HClO_4 solution, the former being added to latter till excess of CdCO_3 remained undissolved. The resulting solution was boiled and filtered. The Cd^{2+} ion concentration was estimated as $\text{Cd}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ by the usual method. Approximately 1.0M solution of NaClO_4 (E. Merck, pure grade) was prepared. Pyridine and picolines (B.D.H., pure grade) were distilled and from the distillate 1.0M solutions of picolines and 2.0M solution of pyridine were prepared. In the preparation of all these solutions, freshly prepared double-distilled water, free from CO_2 , was used. The standardisation of these solutions was carried out potentiometrically, using a standard HCl solution.

Procedure.—The H-type cell, in which the middle compartment was separated by two sintered bed discs, was employed for the determination of the E. M. F. of the different conc. cells, prepared as follows:

The right hand compartment consisted of a ligand, Cd²⁺ ions, 1.0mM in strength, and 0.1M-NaClO₄ solution for keeping ionic strength constant. The different solutions used were prepared by adequately diluting the corresponding stock solutions. The liquid cadmium amalgam, used as an electrode, was prepared by the method described by Vogel ("A Text-book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", p. 317, 2nd ed., Longmans, Green and Co.) and was preserved under 2.0M-H₂SO₄ solution. A portion of this was always washed before use with oxygen-free distilled water and dried with an absorbent paper. It was then immediately poured into right-hand compartment. The necessary precautions were taken to make this compartment completely free of oxygen by incessantly passing oxygen-free nitrogen through the solution for about 20 minutes so that the amalgam never came in contact with oxygen during the experiment. The left-hand side consisted of quinhydrone electrode in 0.01M perchloric acid and the middle compartment was filled with an agar-agar solution saturated with NaClO₄.

A series of readings of the E. M. F. of the combination, prepared as described before, were taken on 'PYE' potentiometer of sensitivity 0.1 mV at various concentrations of the ligands, keeping Cd²⁺ ion concentration constant. The accuracy of the experimental measurements is within ± 0.1 mV. The data were collected at a constant temperature of $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$, using water thermostat controlled by a toluene regulator.

The E. M. F. of such a cell is given by

$$E = E' - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln [M].$$

where E' includes the potential of reference electrode, the liquid junction potential, and a contribution due to activity of metal ions in amalgam electrode and activity coefficients. All the factors were assumed to remain constant throughout the measurements.

When $C_L = 0$, i.e., no ligand is added, the E. M. F. is given by

$$E_1 = E' - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln C_M, \text{ where } C_M = \text{total Cd}^{2+} \text{ ion concentration.}$$

When the ligand is added, some of the Cd²⁺ ions are removed to form a complex and the new potential would be set up. If this new E. M. F. is E_2 , then

$$E_2 = E' - \frac{RT}{nF} \ln [M], \text{ where } [M] = \text{free Cd}^{2+} \text{ ion concentration.}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E = E_2 - E_1 &= \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{C_M}{[M]} \\ &= 0.03 \log_{10} \frac{C_M}{[M]}, \text{ at } 30^\circ. \end{aligned}$$

TABLE I

*Cadmium-pyridine system.*Conc. of $\text{Cd}^{2+}=1.049 \text{ mM}$. Conc. of $\text{NaClO}_4=0.1M$.

[L] (mM).	ΔE (mV).	$\frac{C_M}{[M]}$	F_1 (L).	F_2 (L).	F_3 (L).
50.15	10.0	2.154	23.01	100.00	199.40
98.85	17.6	2.860	28.93	110.56	207.98
161.99	25.8	6.244	38.54	126.81	227.22
233.42	32.8	11.400	48.84	132.10	180.36
309.40	39.3	19.420	62.76	144.69	176.73
392.93	46.0	33.140	84.34	168.84	200.85
487.09	51.4	50.680	104.05	176.65	177.89
588.24	57.0	78.430	133.33	198.06	180.30
686.44	61.6	112.100	163.30	211.68	177.26
792.25	66.8	167.500	211.42	244.14	194.56
882.99	70.6	224.600	254.36	267.68	201.22
961.66	73.3	276.500	287.52	280.27	197.85
			$\beta_1=18$	$\beta_2=90$	$\beta_3=195$

TABLE II

*Cadmium- β -picoline system.*Conc. of $\text{Cd}^{2+}=1.049 \text{ mM}$. Conc. of $\text{NaClO}_4=0.1M$.

[L] (mM).	ΔE (mV).	$\frac{C_M}{[M]}$	F_1 (L).	F_2 (L).	F_3 (L).
19.35	5.7	1.550	28.44	151.90	304.83
45.87	12.0	2.512	32.96	162.61	362.07
71.64	17.1	3.715	37.89	172.94	376.02
107.09	23.0	5.842	45.21	184.05	355.31
146.71	28.5	8.913	53.94	193.85	326.15
185.72	33.0	12.590	62.40	198.69	283.71
234.47	38.4	19.050	76.98	219.56	313.73
278.77	42.8	26.710	92.23	239.37	333.74
322.64	46.4	35.210	106.03	249.60	321.10
372.54	50.5	48.220	126.76	271.78	337.63
424.32	54.0	63.100	146.35	284.81	327.13
482.92	57.5	82.520	168.81	296.26	311.15
			$\beta_1=25.5$	$\beta_2=146$	$\beta_3=345$

TABLE III

*Cadmium- γ -picoline system.*Conc. of $\text{Cd}^{2+}=1.049 \text{ mM}$. Conc. of $\text{NaClO}_4=0.1M$.

[L] (mM).	ΔE (mV).	$\frac{C_M}{[M]}$	F_1 (L).	F_2 (L).	F_3 (L).
7.81	2.9	1.255	32.71	154.40	947.22
27.07	8.9	1.978	36.14	170.82	879.87
42.96	13.0	2.705	39.68	190.37	1009.50
60.80	16.9	3.650	43.58	198.72	850.24
83.36	21.6	5.220	50.63	229.47	999.32
110.99	26.5	7.614	59.59	259.09	955.85
145.25	32.0	11.600	72.97	285.54	953.79
191.13	38.6	19.230	95.38	334.20	979.41
242.62	44.5	30.230	120.47	366.73	905.65
282.05	49.3	43.650	151.21	424.45	983.70
326.82	53.5	60.230	181.23	458.15	952.06
379.53	58.0	85.020	221.39	500.30	930.89
			$\beta_1=31.5$	$\beta_2=147$	$\beta_3=941$

In Tables I to III are recorded the data obtained for the changes in E. M. F. with increasing concentration of ligand and consequent functions, calculated by the method suggested by Leden (*loc. cit.*), as follows:

$$F_1(L) = \frac{C_M}{[M]} - 1 = \beta_1 + \beta_2[L] + \beta_3[L]^2 + \dots + \beta_n[L]^{n-1}$$

$$F_2(L) = \frac{F_1(L) - \beta_1}{[L]} = \beta_2 + \beta_3[L] + \dots + \beta_n[L]^{n-2}$$

$$F_3(L) = \frac{F_2(L) - \beta_2}{[L]} = \beta_3 + \dots + \beta_n[L]^{n-3}$$

$$F_n(L) = \frac{F_{n-1}(L) - \beta_{n-1}}{[L]} = \beta_n \dots$$

where $\beta_n = K_1 \cdot K_2 \cdot K_3 \dots K_n$, K_n being the stability constant of n th stage.

The consecutive overall formation constants β_n were obtained by the extrapolation of the plots of such functions against free ligand conc. $[L]$. A typical extrapolation is given in Fig. 1. β_3 values are taken from the average of $F_3(L)$. The free ligand concentration $[L]$ was assumed to be the same as the total ligand concentration C_L , which is permissible in such weak complexes. In Table IV, the data evaluated for the stepwise stability constants K_n are surveyed.

FIG. 1. Cd^{2+} -pyridine.

TABLE IV

Ligand.	pK_a .	$\text{Log } K_1$.	$\text{Log } K_2$.	$\text{Log } K_3$.	$\text{Log } \beta_3$.
Pyridine	5.17	1.26	0.70	0.34	2.29
β -Picoline	5.68	1.41	0.76	0.37	2.54
γ -Picoline	6.02	1.50	0.67	0.81	2.97

DISCUSSION

Data in Tables I to IV show that the complex formation takes place between Cd^{2+} ions and pyridine, β -picoline, and γ -picoline, the metal ion to ligand ratio being 1:1, 1:2, and 1:3. Although Bailar *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) reported the existence of 1:4 complex in Cd^{2+} —pyridine system, but under the conditions of the present investigation no evidence was obtained for such complex.

The values of the stability constants for Cd^{2+} —pyridine are observed to be in fair agreement with those obtained by Morinaga (*loc. cit.* Cf. $\beta_1=23$, $\beta_2=90$, and $\beta_3=187$). In the light of these observations the higher value of $\beta_3=574$, determined by Liu and Fu (*loc. cit.*), appears to be somewhat surprising.

Table IV points out that the stability constants of the different complexes lie in the ligand order: γ -picoline $>$ β -picoline $>$ pyridine. This order compares very well with that of their pK_a values (Brown and Mihm, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 1723). Incidentally, the plot of $\log K_1$ against pK_a was found to be a straight line (Fig. 2). The increase in the stability of picoline complexes can be attributed to the electron donating nature of the $-\text{CH}_3$ group which augments the corresponding electron-donating tendency of the heterocyclic nitrogen, the co-ordinating site of the ligands. The increased stability of β -picoline is due to the inductive effect of the $-\text{CH}_3$ group. In case of γ -picoline complexes, in addition to this inductive effect, there is also a mesomeric effect contributing towards their greater stability.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

1. Cd^{2+} —pyridine.
2. " — β -picoline.
3. " — γ -picoline.

A large number of data is available on the Ag^+ —complexes of these ligands, the stabilities of which can be compared with those of the Cd^{2+} —complexes reported in this investigation. It is ordinarily expected that on account of the increased charge on the ion, Cd^{2+} —complexes may be more stable than their Ag^+ counterparts. The observation, however, is not in keeping with this expectation and can hardly be explained entirely on the basis of the difference between their ionic radii and the polarizing action of the central metal ions. Notwithstanding this, the following explanation may account for this observation.

Very recently, Yatsimirski ("Instability Constants of Complex Compounds", p. 69, Pergamon Press, 1960) and Irving ("The Stability of Metal Complexes", International Conference on Co-ordination Chemistry, London, April 6-11, 1959, p. 13, Chemical Society, London, Pub. No. 13) have pointed out that when dative π -bond is formed inside the complex particle between the ligand and the central atom, the exceptional behaviour as recorded above is noted. This happens because the strength of the π -bond decreases with increase in the charge of the central ion.

An attempt at the application of the empirical equation of Van Panthaleon and Van Eck (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1953, 72, 529) for the stepwise stability constants,

$$\log K_n = \log K_1 - 2\lambda(n-1)$$

(where ' λ ' is constant and ' n ', the number of attached ligands), to the present data did not meet with success. Fig. 3 shows that $\log K_2$ values are lower than the requisite ones for them to lie on a straight line plot of $\log K_n$ against $(n-1)$. This finding was then examined from another angle. The change in the magnitude of stepwise constants with the change in the number of ligands is also determined by the stereochemical characteristics of the compounds concerned. Cd^{2+} ion is generally known to form a tetrahedral structure with complexing ligands as there is no vacant d -orbital for the formation of planar or octahedral configuration. Viewed from this point, one is struck with the fact that a dipole-dipole interaction would occur between the ligands in the species ML_2 when they are situated at the apices of a tetrahedron. This may give rise to a sort of repulsive effect which would operate to a greater extent in a tetrahedral than in a planar or octahedral structure, thereby decreasing the second stability constant. This observation is in agreement with that of Yatsimirski (*loc. cit.*) in the case of tetrahedral co-ordination.

The similar studies with α -picoline show that the complex formed must have been very weak, as the cadmium hydroxide is invariably found to precipitate owing to hydrolysis, which predominates here over complex formation. This behaviour is distinctly different from that of Ag^+ -complexes of α -picoline, the stability of which is of the same order of corresponding Ag^+ -complexes of β - and γ -picolines. The probable explanation is that in α position a sufficiently large $-\text{CH}_3$ group offers a steric hindrance to Cd^{2+} ion for the formation of the possible tetrahedral complex. In case of Ag^+ -complex of α -picoline, such a possibility cannot exist as the structure would be linear.

Grateful acknowledgements are due to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Govt. of India, for the award of a senior research scholarship to one of the authors (A. G. Desai).